

A STATISTICAL STUDY OF THE VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH CONCENTRATION OF ELECTROLYTES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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When specific conductivity μ of aqueous solutions of electrolytes is plotted against the percentage concentration c , in a large number of cases it has been observed that the curve passes through a maximum which lies in most cases between 20% and 30% concentration. On a statistical study it has been found that electrolytes, in general, can be grouped into two broad divisions. The first one includes electrolytes without a maximum in the conductivity-concentration (μ - c) curves: to this category belong the alkali (except Li) and ammonium salts of inorganic acids (HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HBr and HI). To the second class belong most of the soluble electrolytes e.g. LiCl, CuCl₂, Cu(NO₃)₂, CuSO₄, CaCl₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, and ZnCl₂, etc. all the acetates, carbonates, acids, and hydroxides etc. It has been further observed that, in general, for the same anion and different cations the maximum occurs at almost the same equivalent percentage concentration. An attempt has been made to explain the above facts on the ionic hydration hypothesis as modified in the light of recent theories.

In connection with some work on supersaturation, the specific conductivities of aqueous solutions of KNO₃, KCl, K₂SO₄ and sodium acetate were determined at different temperatures on the lines followed by Heim (*Ann. physikal. Chem.*, 1886, *iii*, 27, 613). While the specific conductivity—concentration curves at a given temperature were found to be straight lines in the first three cases, the curves for sodium acetate given below in Fig. 1 passed through a maximum at all the five temperatures tried. The maximum observed appeared to have nothing to do with the saturation or labile temperatures and it was always found to lie somewhere near 24% concentration which increased slightly with temperature.

TABLE I.

Sulphates.			Chlorides.			Nitrates.		
	% Composition			% Composition.			% Composition.	
	Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.
*Cu	22.5%	0.2900	Li	18.0%	0.4216	*Mg.	22.5%	0.3102
Zn	24.0	0.2970	Mg	20.0	0.4246	Ca	25.0	0.3048
Cd.	30.0	0.2885	Ca	23.0	0.4144	Sr	30.0	0.2840
Mg	17.5	0.2910	Mn	23.0	0.3600	Cu	30.0	0.3199
			Cu	24.0	0.3600	Cd	35.0	0.2900
			Cd	25.0	0.2750 (?)			
			Zn	27.0	0.4040			

* By extrapolation.

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It appears from the above table that the maximum in most cases lies between 20% and 30% concentration.

TABLE II.

Inorganic acids.			Aliphatic organic acids.			Chloreactic acids.		
	% Composition.			% Composition.			% Composition.	
	Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.
Nitric	30.0%	0.4800	Formic	30.0%	0.6510	Acetic	15.0%	0.2490
Hydrochloric	19.0	0.5230	Acetic	15.0	0.2490	Monochlor ..	19.6	0.1961
Sulphuric	30.0	0.6120	Propionic	12.0	0.1700	Dichlor ..	22.5	0.1732
Phosphoric	46.0	1.5300	Butyric	11.0	0.2100	Trichlor ..	33.0	0.1700
Alkalis			Alkalis			Alkalis		
	% Composition.			% Composition.			% Composition.	
	Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.		Max.	Min.
KOH	28.0%	0.4998	NaOH	16.0%	0.4000	NH ₄ OH	5.0%	0.3000

On referring to the literature a number of others electrolytes were found which exhibited this behaviour, while certain other appeared to be similar to KCl, KNO₃ and K₂SO₄. To the former type belong all the soluble acetates, carbonates, hydroxides and acids, soluble chlorides, sulphates, and nitrates of Li, Cu, Ca, Sr, Zn Al etc., while to the latter belong the sulphates, nitrates, chlorides, bromides and iodides of alkali (except Li) and ammonium cations.

In order to get further information about this behaviour, conductivity-concentration (μ - c) curves, similar to those in Fig. 1, are obtained from data collected from Landolt-Bornstein Tables (Ed. 1912) and are given below.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 1.

Similar curves have been obtained for a number of other electrolytes but only the results deduced therefrom are tabulated below along with those obtained for substances given in Figs. 2 and 3.

In all the tables given above, % concentrations at the maximum, and at the maximum are in g. equivalents.

The curves and tables given above lead to the following conclusions :

Specific conductivity μ appears to shoot out in a straight line from the zero concentration. The later course of the curve depends, however, on the nature of the electrolyte in solution.

The μ - c curves, in general, pass through a maximum in all cases excepting the alkali and ammonium salts of inorganic acid. The curves for sodium and ammonium salts, however, have a tendency to bend towards the concentration axis (Fig. 2).

Sulphates, nitrates and chlorides of Cu, Li, Zn, Cd, and Mg etc. show that for the same anion and different cations in general, the maximum, occurs at approximately the same equivalent percentage concentration. For sulphates this concentration is 0.2900, for nitrates 0.3010, and for chlorides 0.4100 approximately.

The equivalent percentage concentration at the maximum for inorganic acids increases in the following order : $\text{HNO}_3 < \text{HCl} < \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 < \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$.

The maximum in the aliphatic organic acids occurs in the following increasing order : $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{COOH} < \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOH} < \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} < \text{H}^+\text{COOH}$.

But this quantity for chloro-substituted acetic acids decreases with increasing amount of chlorine in the methyl group : $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} > \text{CH}_2\text{ClCOOH} > \text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH} > \text{CCl}_3\text{COOH}$; and for hydroxides it increases in the order : $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} < \text{NaOH} < \text{KOH}$.

DISCUSSION

Crompton and Armstrong (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 116) were the first to recognise the maximum in the μ - c curves of aqueous solutions of a number of substances and took it to be an evidence of the existence of definite hydrates in solutions, thereby supporting the hydration hypothesis of Mendeleef (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 379 *et seq.*). But as the hydration theory of solutions was gradually replaced by the "Dissociation hypothesis" (*cf.* Arrhenius, *Phil. Mag.*, 1889, 28, 3038), Crompton's suggestions could not be taken seriously. Later, Jones noticed the maximum in the μ - c curves of aqueous solutions of CoCl_2 and CuCl_2 in presence of different dehydrating agents and ascribed it to be due to increase in viscosity of solutions as a result of addition of dehydrating agents (Jones, "Hydrates in Aqueous Solutions", 1904, p. 840). However, this explanation is insufficient to cover all the facts pointed out herein, specially as it has been applied to solutions of mixtures of electrolytes of a particular nature but not to those of single substances.

Comparatively recently the researches of various authors have established the existence of hydrated ions in aqueous solutions. An attempt has been made below to show that the results arrived at from a close study of μ - c curves can be explained, in general, from the viewpoint of hydration of ions.

Ionic Interaction and the Hydrated Ions.

As mentioned above the chlorides, nitrates, and sulphates of Na, NH_4 and K do not exhibit any maximum in the μ - c curves but the corresponding acids do. Also all the soluble acetates, carbonates and all the soluble salts of Ca, Cu, Cd, Zn, Fe,

Al etc., in general, show the maximum. If the ionic interaction is the main cause of the fall in μ with increase in concentration then the maximum should also occur in the μ - c curves of alkali and ammonium salts of inorganic acids at approximately similar concentrations. Even allowing for the sizes of the ions, there must be some curvature in the curves of K-salts of inorganic acids as a result of electrical attraction. The almost straight line nature of these curves rules out the possibility of any major effect of interionic attraction which, however, can not be totally neglected and it will certainly play a subsidiary rôle in reducing μ with increase in c . It may add to the hydration effect as both the phenomena appear to go hand-in-hand.

Various researches appear to show that, in general, K^+ , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , SO_4^{--} , Cl^- , Br^- , and I^- ions have a smaller affinity for water molecules than Li^+ , Ca^{++} , Sr^{++} , Cu^{++} , Mg^{++} , Zn^{++} , Fe^{++} , Fe^{+++} , Al^{+++} etc. Sudgen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 174, 196) even goes to the extent of assuming that anions are not hydrated at all. The majority of workers consider, however, that at least SO_4^{--} and F^- are hydrated. Apart from hydration hypothesis of Fajans and others, a more recent conception of hydration is obtained from the entropies of different ions in aqueous solutions. The following table (Rice, "Electronic Structure and Chemical Binding", 1940, p. 480) gives the entropies of different ions, which are supposed to be dissolved in water from gaseous state, in aqueous solution.

TABLE III.

Ion.	$\Delta S.$	Ion.	$\Delta S.$	Ion.	$\Delta S.$	Ion.	$\Delta S.$
H^+	-24.3	Mg^{++}	-70.0	Pb^{++}	-40.8	I^-	-4.2
Li^+	-25.3	Ca^{++}	-51.2	Fe^{++}	(-69.0)	S^-	-26.2
Na^+	-19.6	Ba^{++}	-41.2	Fe^{+++}	(-112)		
K^+	-11.0	Cu^{++}	(-69.0)	Al^{+++}	(-119.2)		
Rb^+	-8.8	Cd^{++}	-59.3	F^-	-25.1		
Ag^+	-20.7	Hg^{++}	-51.1	Cl^-	-12.2		
Tl^+	-9.6	Sr^{++}	-48.0	Br^-	-8.6		

[Figures in parenthesis are doubtful.]

The above table reveals that Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Tl^+ , Cl^- , Br^- and I^- have higher entropy values (+ ΔS) as compared to Mg^{++} , Cu^{++} , Sr^{++} , Ba^{++} , Ca^{++} , Cd^{++} , Fe^{++} , Al^{+++} etc., whereas Li^+ and H^+ have a value approximately half that of the most of the divalent cations. Higher entropy means a greater freedom of movement in the medium *i.e.*, less attachment with the solvent molecules and hence less hydration and *vice versa*.

As entropy is an additive function, their values for the counter-ions of any salt can be added which should give, in general, the resultant hydration effect for that particular salt. By comparing these values for different salts, an idea of the relative hydration can be obtained as is clear from Table IV.

TABLE IV.
Total ionic entropies of
some halides.

Cation.	F.	Cl.	Br.	I.	
Na ⁺	-45.7	-31.8	-28.2	-23.8	
K ⁺	-37.0	-23.2	-19.6	-15.2	
Rb ⁺	-34.9	-21.0	-17.4	-13.0	
Tl ⁺	-35.6	-21.8	-18.2	-13.8	Group I
H ⁺	-50.4	-36.5	-32.9	-28.2	
Li ⁺	-51.4	-37.5	-33.9	-29.5	
$\frac{1}{2}$ Ca ⁺⁺	-51.7	-37.8	-34.2	-29.8	
$\frac{1}{2}$ Mg ⁺⁺	-61.1	-47.2	-43.6	-39.2	
$\frac{1}{2}$ Cu ⁺⁺	-60.6	-46.7	-43.1	-38.7	Group II
$\frac{1}{2}$ Cd ⁺⁺	-55.7	-41.8	-38.2	-33.8	Group I
$\frac{1}{2}$ Al ⁺⁺⁺	-65.8	-57.9	-48.3	-43.2	
$\frac{1}{2}$ Fe ⁺⁺⁺	-63.4	-49.5	-45.9	-41.5	

TABLE V.
Heats of hydration of halides
of different cations.

Cation.	F.	Cl.	Br.	I.	
Na ⁺	242.8	203.6	192.1	181.2	
K ⁺	223.6	184.3	172.9	162.2	Group I
Tl ⁺	246.1	206.9	195.6	184.8	
Ag ⁺	240.9	208.6	197.9	186.5	
Li ⁺	276.3	237.1	225.9	215.2	
Mg ⁺⁺	750.0	672.3	649.7	630.0	
Ca ⁺⁺	650.9	570.2	547.9	526.1	
Sr ⁺⁺	620.3	540.1	517.8	496.4	Group II
Ba ⁺⁺	573.1	493.5	471.0	449.6	
Zn ⁺⁺	...	731.2	708.6	688.9	
Cd ⁺⁺	...	678.2	656.8	639.8	
Hg ⁺⁺	...	698.1	677.0	666.0	
Pb ⁺⁺	...	598.0	575.6	558.0	

It can be easily concluded from Table IV that alkali halides, in general, are less hydrated than other halides ($\Delta S < \text{or} = -34$ approx.). Similar results are expected for the salts of other inorganic acids and above cations.

Assuming that a higher heat of hydration implies a greater affinity between water molecules and ions *i.e.*, assuming that the Thomsen-Berthelot principle is applicable to such systems, a rough idea of the relative extent of hydration can be obtained from the works of Butler (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 113, 285) as is clear from Table. V.

To illustrate the above point consider the different halides of lithium. Li⁺ ion is common in all cases (and hence its heat of hydration); obviously, then, the hydration of the halide ions occurs in the order: F⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > I⁻. Similarly by taking an anion common it may be seen that: (Li⁺ > Tl⁺ > Na⁺ > Ag⁺ > K⁺) < (Zn⁺⁺ > Cd⁺⁺ > Mg⁺⁺ > Hg⁺⁺ > Pb⁺⁺ > Ca⁺⁺ > Sr⁺⁺ > Ba⁺⁺). It may be pointed out, however, that the values of the heats of hydration of ions have been obtained indirectly from the lattice energy and the heat of solution by the method developed by Fajans (*Ber. physikal. Ges.*, 1919, 21, 549).

Assuming then, that the maximum in the μ - c curves is due to hydration of anions and cations as postulated above and also that this hydration effect is an additive function of the cation and anion in question, it will be easy to explain the nature of the different types of μ - c curves as considered above. Firstly, the alkali and ammonium salts of common inorganic acids, in general, do not show a maximum in the μ - c curves because the cation and anion in each case are only very slightly hydrated. A bending round in the curves of sodium and ammonium salts is indicative of a greater hydration of Na⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions as compared to that of K⁺-ion. Specially notable is the case of KF ($\Delta S = -37$). A maximum in its μ - c curve occurs at about

35% concentration due to the F^- ion being highly hydrated which makes the total entropy of KF as low as 37. On the other hand, in LiI, whose entropy value is only -29.5 , the maximum should occur at a higher concentration as is suggested by its $\mu-c$ curve. Hence additivity of ionic hydration, in so far as its effect on μ is concerned, is very clearly brought out by these two examples.

A comparatively high hydration of Ca^{++} , Sr^{++} , Cu^{++} , Mg^{++} , Zn^{++} , and Al^{+++} etc. brings about the maximum in the $\mu-c$ curves at concentrations below 30% in most cases. Here again CdI_2 shows an abnormality due to the very small hydration of the iodide ion ($\Delta S = -42$). It must be added, however, that the iodides of all these cations will behave similarly if their solubility allows experimental investigation. The course of the curve for CdI_2 , however, suggests that the maximum may occur at about 60% concentration.

Min. column I of Table I show that for the same anion and different cations, the maximum occurs at almost the same equivalent percentage concentration in most

FIG. 3.

cases. This indicates that the cations concerned are, in general, almost equally hydrated. It must be pointed out, however, that as the maximum occurs at almost the same equivalent percentage concentration, hydration of Li^+ ion is about one-half of the rest. As a result of the effect of the hydration of different anions, this concentration is different for different anions *e.g.*, for chloride 0.4100, for sulphate 0.2900, and for nitrate 0.3010 approximately.

In the case of inorganic acids and chloro-substituted acetic acids it appears that the stronger the acid, the lower the equivalent percentage concentration at which the maximum occurs. Stronger acids will have a higher effective hydrogen-ion concentration and hence would involve a greater number of water molecules in the hydration process. Consequently the maximum shifts to lower concentrations due to increase in the effective mass of the ion as well as in the resistance to their movement in the medium. The anions of the acids, however, will add to this according to their hydration. In spite of the fact that various workers consider the hydrogen-ion to be least hydrated, conclusions, arrived at in this paper and supported by a number of researches, appear to show that the H^+ ion is sufficiently hydrated.

On the other hand in the case of aliphatic organic acids, the weaker the acid, the lower the equivalent percentage concentration at which the maximum occurs.

It is likely that this behaviour is due to polymerisation of the acid molecules. The weaker the acid, the greater the polymerisation and hence lower the concentration at which the maximum is reached due to abnormal disappearance of ions from the field of action. It may be added that these polymerised molecules or 'micelles' are hydrated and this adds a great deal to the viscosity of the solutions (Tsaklotos, *Compt. rend.*, 1940, 2, 805). But probably the polymerisation of the acid molecules is the more predominant factor in these cases. We see, therefore, that it is possible to explain, in general, the nature of the specific conductivity—percentage concentration curves of solutions of electrolytes in water on the ionic hydration hypothesis as modified in the light of recent researches.

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